

Building a Literate Generation: The Effectiveness of Morning Literacy in Honing the Reading Comprehension Ability of Junior High School Students

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the morning literacy program in improving the reading comprehension ability of students of SMP Negeri 6 Semarang. A mixed methods approach with an exploratory sequential design was used in this study, which consisted of qualitative data collection through observation, questionnaires, and interviews, followed by quantitative data collection through reading comprehension tests. The results of the study show that the implementation of routine morning literacy is carried out but not optimal, with an average score of 60% of students' reading comprehension ability, which is below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). The main causative factors include the lack of variety in literacy activities, less intensive interaction between students and teachers, and limited variety of reading materials. This study recommends increasing the variety of literacy activities, enriching reading resources, and active involvement of teachers to improve literacy learning outcomes. The implication of this study is that the implementation of a more effective morning literacy program can improve the quality of learning in general, especially in developing students' critical and analytical thinking skills.

Keywords: *Morning literacy, reading comprehension, mixed methods, interactive learning, junior high school.*

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Introduction

Introduction Reading comprehension is one of the key competencies that must be mastered by students to support academic success and the development of critical skills in the current information and technology era (De-Juanas Oliva et al., 2016; H. Madani, 2016). Reading literacy not only involves passive reading of texts but also includes the active ability to understand, analyze, evaluate, interpret, and apply information in various real-life contexts (Banditvilai, 2020; Pourhosein Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016). This skill is becoming increasingly important considering the need for understanding complex texts in the world of education which requires students to be able to think critically and analytically (Chalkiadaki, 2018; R. A. Madani, 2019). However, the facts that emerge from the results of international studies such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2022 show that Indonesia is still lagging behind other countries in the aspect of reading literacy (Argina et al., 2017; Chamdani et al., 2019). The low score reflects the existence of fundamental problems in reading culture, text comprehension skills, and literacy learning strategies implemented in schools in Indonesia (Argina et al., 2017; Pokropek et al., 2022). Realizing the importance of this, the Indonesian government has taken strategic steps through the School Literacy Movement (GLS), which aims to build a systematic reading culture, one of which is through a morning literacy habituation program that is carried out regularly in the school environment before starting learning activities (Castañer & Oliveira, 2020; Wandasari et al., 2019).

SMP Negeri 6 Semarang is one of the educational institutions that has consistently implemented the morning literacy habituation program as an integral part of the implementation of GLS. This school strives to create an environment conducive to the growth of reading interest and improve students' reading comprehension skills through routine activities every morning. However, the implementation of this program has not been accompanied by a comprehensive and systematic evaluation to assess the extent of its impact on improving students' reading comprehension skills (Chambers et al., 2016; Kremmel & Harding, 2020). In fact, reading comprehension is very important because it not only has a direct impact on student learning outcomes in various subjects, but is also a basic skill to face more complex academic challenges such as computer-based national assessments (ANBK) (Elleman & Oslund, 2019; Iordache et al., 2017; H. Madani, 2016; Pourhosein Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016; Timmis et al., 2016). In addition, high reading comprehension is also an important foundation for students in developing high-level thinking skills, such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving (Khoiriyah & Husamah, 2018; Smith et al., 2021; Wechsler et al., 2018). Therefore, in-depth and structured research on the effectiveness and real impact of morning literacy habituation is very relevant to determine the effectiveness of this program and provide concrete input for improving the quality of literacy learning in SMP Negeri 6 Semarang in particular, and in Indonesian schools in general.

This study specifically aims to describe in detail and systematically how students' reading comprehension ability after the implementation of morning literacy habituation at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang. This study uses a mixed methods approach with an exploratory sequential research design, which aims not only to reveal the results quantitatively but also to explore in depth qualitative aspects related to various internal factors such as reading interest, learning motivation, and external factors such as the availability of reading resources and the role of teachers in the literacy process (Antony et al., 2023; Berman, 2017; Dawadi et al., 2021; Fitria, 2019; Plano Clark, 2017). This approach allows researchers to obtain a holistic picture of the effectiveness of the

morning literacy habituation program and the obstacles faced. The results of this study are expected to provide strategic recommendations that can be used by schools and policy makers in optimizing the implementation of GLS. Thus, this research has the potential to be an important reference in order to improve the quality of literacy nationally, help schools design more effective literacy activities, and provide guidance in formulating educational policies related to the development of sustainable reading literacy.

Literature Review

Literature Review Reading comprehension is defined as a student's ability to understand, evaluate, and interpret written information in depth and critically (Changwong et al., 2018; Waugh et al., 2016; Wechsler et al., 2018). (Banditvilai, 2020; H. Madani, 2016) explained that reading comprehension is an active process in which the reader not only absorbs information but also actively builds meaning based on previous experience and knowledge. In addition, (Banditvilai, 2020; Elleman & Oslund, 2019; Saidah & Damariswara, 2021) stated that good reading ability is closely related to students' academic achievement in various subject areas because this ability allows students to access new knowledge effectively and efficiently. The importance of this ability is reinforced by the research of (Banditvilai, 2020; Pourhosein Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016) which shows a significant correlation between reading comprehension skills and students' academic achievement in various fields of study.

The habit of morning literacy as part of GLS is designed to create a strong reading culture from an early age in the school environment (Antoro, 2017; Muhammad, 2017). Several studies show that consistent reading habits have a positive impact on improving students' reading interest and reading skills (R. A. Madani, 2019; Rokmana et al., 2023). However, the implementation of GLS faces various challenges in the field such as a limited variety of reading materials that are interesting to students, a lack of literacy support facilities such as libraries and reading corners, and suboptimal teacher training on effective literacy methods (Anderson, 2018; Chambers et al., 2016). Research conducted by (Liyanawatta et al., 2022) also highlights the importance of using digital technology to increase student involvement in literacy activities.

Furthermore, a study conducted by (H. Madani, 2016; Ruiz, 2015; Smith et al., 2021) found that students' reading comprehension skills can be improved through pedagogical interventions that focus on intensive and interactive reading activities. Learning strategies such as class discussions, presentations of reading results, and the use of digital media have proven to be effective in developing students' critical thinking skills and reading comprehension. Another study conducted by (Briggs et al., 2019; Means, 2025) also emphasizes the need for an integrative and sustainable approach to literacy implementation, involving all stakeholders in the educational environment to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of literacy habituation programs in schools. In addition, recent research shows that family and community support also greatly determines the success of school literacy programs. Therefore, cross-sector collaboration between schools, families, and communities is urgently needed to create a conducive literacy ecosystem.

Method

Research Methods This study uses a mixed methods approach with an exploratory sequential design that involves the collection of qualitative data followed by quantitative data collection. The use of this mixed method allows researchers to explore phenomena in more depth and provide more comprehensive research results. The first stage in the form of qualitative data collection was carried out through observation of the implementation of morning literacy activities, in-depth interviews with teachers and students, and the dissemination of questionnaires that aimed to explore information about the implementation of literacy habituation, students' perception of morning literacy activities, and factors that support or hinder its implementation. This qualitative data is then used to develop more relevant quantitative instruments, such as reading comprehension tests, in order to obtain more measurable data related to students' reading comprehension skills.

This study involved two main variables, namely the dependent variable in the form of students' reading comprehension ability and the independent variable in the form of morning literacy habituation. The population in this study is all students in grade VIII of SMP Negeri 6 Semarang which totals 8 classes. The sampling technique used is cluster random sampling, by randomly selecting one class that represents the population. The data collection techniques used include observations to record the process and implementation of morning literacy habituation, questionnaires to identify students' perceptions of literacy activities, semi-structured interviews with students and teachers to obtain in-depth information and data triangulation, and reading comprehension tests to measure students' skill levels after morning literacy activities are routinely carried out.

The research procedure begins with problem identification and problem formulation followed by a comprehensive theoretical study to strengthen the conceptual basis of the research. Then qualitative data collection was carried out in the form of direct observation of the implementation of literacy habituation, the distribution of questionnaires to students to find out students' perceptions and interest in the morning literacy program, as well as in-depth interviews with teachers and students to confirm the questionnaire and observation data. Furthermore, quantitative data was collected through a reading comprehension test to measure the extent of students' achievement after participating in the morning literacy habituation. The data analysis technique in this study follows the Miles and Huberman interactive analysis model which includes the data collection stage, data reduction to sort out relevant data, presentation of data in narrative and tables, as well as drawing conclusions and verifying research findings systematically. The research procedure is illustrated in figure 1.

The validity of the data is maintained through the method triangulation technique, which is to confirm the results of various data collection methods (observation, questionnaire, and interview) so that valid and reliable data are obtained. Triangulation of this method ensures that the results of the study are reliable and provides an accurate picture of the reality being studied. In addition, the validation of the content of the test instrument is also carried out through expert judgment to ensure that the research instrument is really able to measure the reading comprehension ability of students effectively and accurately. Data analysis was carried out through an interactive approach of the Miles and Huberman model which consisted of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing and verification.

Figure 1. Research Procedure Sequence

In the reduction stage, data from observations, questionnaires, and interviews are selected and sorted based on relevance to the research objectives. The presentation of data is carried out in a narrative manner and is supported by tables that clarify the research findings. To maintain the validity of the data, a triangulation technique was used, namely by comparing data from observations, questionnaires, and interviews to ensure the accuracy of the research results. In addition, the validation of the content of the test instrument is carried out through expert judgment so that it can accurately measure the student's reading comprehension.

Figure 2. Data Analysis Procedures (Milles & Huberman)

Research Results

Results and Discussion The results of the study show that morning literacy habituation activities at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang have taken place regularly. Based on the results of observation, students brought their own books which were dominated by fiction books, such as novels and short stories. Literacy activities last about 10-20 minutes every day. However, the activities carried out by students are still limited to reading independently without any significant interaction, such as class discussions or in-depth presentations. This situation resulted in only 2-3 students actively delivering reading

results every day. This activity illustrates the implementation of literacy which is still limited to the habituation stage without follow-up to deepen student understanding.

Implementation of Morning Literacy Activities

Results and Discussion The results of the study show that morning literacy habituation activities at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang have taken place regularly. Based on the results of observation, students brought their own books which were dominated by fiction books, such as novels and short stories. Literacy activities last about 10-20 minutes every day. However, the activities carried out by students are still limited to reading independently without any significant interaction, such as class discussions or in-depth presentations. This situation resulted in only 2-3 students actively delivering reading results every day. This activity illustrates the implementation of literacy which is still limited to the habituation stage without follow-up to deepen student understanding. In practice, students bring their own reading books, the majority of which are fiction types such as novels or short stories (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Students Get into the Habit of Reading Morning at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang

However, this activity is still limited to individual reading without significant follow-up activities, such as group discussions or presentations of reading content. Student involvement in the delivery of reading results is also still low, with an average of only 2-3 students actively delivering reading content every day. This shows that the implementation of morning literacy is still procedural without further exploration to deepen students' reading comprehension skills.

Students' Perception and Interest in Literacy Activities

The results of the questionnaire showed that the majority of students had a less positive perception of morning literacy activities. Students feel less interested because the activities are monotonous and the time provided is only about 10-20 minutes is considered insufficient to understand the reading content optimally. Table 1 shows that most students rarely take extra time to read outside of class hours, which reflects that literacy habituation has not fully succeeded in creating a strong reading culture.

Table 1. Students' Responses in Reading Literacy

No.	Statement	Highest Percentage
1	At school, reading and writing literacy is always held	Yes
2	Time allotted for reading and writing literacy	10 minutes
3	The school provides reading books for students	Materials only
4	Literacy activities are held every ... Sunday	1
5	Time needed to be able to understand the content of the book takes time	10 minutes
6	How many books do you read in one day less than 1 book	Less than 1 book
7	How often students read material books in school	Sometimes
8	Students love literacy activities	Less
9	Students are required to have a reading book	Not
10	Students have been asked to bring non-lesson books	Sometimes
11	Students often spend time outside of class hours to be literate	Sometimes
12	Participants always take the time to read books in the library	Not
13	The school has programs other than literacy to develop an interest in reading and writing skills	Exist
14	Teachers often ask about the contents of books that have been read directly	Sometimes
15	The teacher tells students to convey the content of the book they have read, directly in front of the class	Sometimes
16	Participants were encouraged to like literacy activities	Less
17	Students are required to have a reading book	Not
18	Students have been asked to bring non-lesson books	Ever
19	Students often spend time outside of class hours to be literate	Not
20	Students always take time to read books in the library	Not

In-depth interviews with students and teachers shed light on the various findings that emerged in observations and questionnaires. Most respondents confirmed that morning literacy activities were routinely carried out, but their implementation was not optimal. The students complained about the lack of variety of books available, especially non-textbooks that can attract students' interest in reading. They also said that appreciation or appreciation that encourages students' motivation to read is almost non-existent, causing low interest and enthusiasm for students to be actively involved in literacy activities. Teachers also admit that there is no sustainable literacy development program, and there has been no special training for teachers in effective literacy strategies.

The results of the quantitative test showed that students' reading comprehension ability was in the low category with an average score of 60%, which was still below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). This low achievement shows that the morning literacy habituation carried out at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang has not been able to significantly improve students' reading comprehension skills. The factors that cause these low achievements include the lack of variety of reading books, lack of interaction in morning literacy activities, lack of active involvement of teachers in guiding students, and the absence of adequate rewards for students who show achievement or consistency in reading. Based on these findings, it is necessary to carry out interventions that include diversifying reading materials, organizing group discussion activities or presentations, and increasing the role of teachers as facilitators in morning literacy activities so that this activity can have a positive impact on students' reading comprehension ability optimally.

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Morning Literacy

Based on the results of in-depth interviews with students and teachers, it was revealed that several factors caused the implementation of morning literacy to be not optimal. Internal factors such as low interest in reading and student motivation to be actively involved in literacy activities are the main challenges. External factors in the form of limited reading sources that vary in schools are also an obstacle. Schools mostly only provide subject matter books, while the collection of non-subject books or other references is still very limited. In addition, the lack of appreciation or appreciation for students who are actively literate reduces the enthusiasm and motivation of students to participate optimally. Another factor is the absence of a special program for sustainable literacy development and the lack of teacher training in effective literacy methods.

Table 2. Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Morning Literacy Implementation

It	Influencing Factors	Category	Description
1	Students' interest in reading and motivation	Internal	Lack of enthusiasm for students in morning literacy activities due to low interest in reading.
2	Variety of reading sources	External	There are only a limited number of types of reading books available, most of which are only textbooks and fiction.
3	Appreciation for active students	External	There is no special award for students who are regular and active in literacy.
4	Literacy development programs	External	There is no sustainable program to improve the quality of student literacy.
5	Teacher training on literacy methods	External	Teachers have not received special training in effective literacy strategies.

This table makes it clear that internal factors in the form of low motivation and interest in reading students are the main challenges that affect the effectiveness of the implementation of morning literacy. This internal factor is closely related to external factors such as limited reading variety and lack of appreciation for students. For this reason, the solution that needs to be taken is to enrich the collection of readings that are relevant to students' interests, such as popular scientific readings, biographies, and other inspirational readings. In addition, giving appreciation through simple awards and formal awards for students who are actively literate can increase students' intrinsic motivation. Continuous literacy development programs and special training for teachers are also very important to create a more effective, dynamic, and conducive literacy learning environment.

Level of Reading Comprehension Ability of Students

The results of the quantitative test show that the reading comprehension ability of SMP Negeri 6 Semarang students is still relatively low with an average score of 60%, below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). This low achievement deeply indicates that the current implementation of morning literacy is not effective in stimulating students' critical understanding of the reading content. Based on in-depth analysis, students have difficulty identifying the main idea, finding the main sentence, and drawing the right conclusion from the given reading. This condition is closely related to the lack of active involvement of students in activities that support understanding, such as discussions or presentations of reading results in front of the

class. Students are more likely to do reading activities passively, without any interaction that encourages critical thinking and reflection on the content of the reading.

Figure 4. Distribution Graph of Students' Reading Comprehension Score

Based on the graph above, it is known that the reading comprehension ability of SMP Negeri 6 Semarang students is still mostly below the ideal criteria. The majority of students scored in the range of 60-70, with the highest frequency being around 65. These findings indicate that most students have not fully mastered the ability to understand reading content optimally after following the habit of morning literacy regularly. Although there are some students who manage to achieve high scores (around 85-90), the number is relatively small compared to the group of students who are still in the low to medium category. This shows that the morning literacy habit that has been carried out so far is still not able to effectively improve reading comprehension skills significantly. Additional interventions are needed such as a variety of reading sources, active involvement of teachers in literacy development, and additional programs that can encourage increased interest and motivation of students in reading comprehension activities in schools

In addition, the lack of variety of available reading sources directly affects the low enthusiasm of students in exploring more complex and challenging texts. The limited reading materials dominated by simple fiction books cause students to be unfamiliar with various types of more complex and informative texts. The lack of training and the active role of teachers as literacy facilitators are also critical factors. Teachers who are not active in guiding students to understand and evaluate the reading content in depth make it difficult to achieve the goal of morning literacy optimally. Therefore, structured interventions are needed in the form of a variety of interactive literacy activities, enrichment of a wider collection of non-textbook readings, and intensive training for teachers on literacy strategies so that students are able to develop reading comprehension skills optimally.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the morning literacy program at SMP Negeri 6 Semarang has been routinely implemented,

but has not achieved optimal results in improving students' reading comprehension skills. This can be seen from the average score of students' reading comprehension ability of 60%, which is still below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). The main factors that cause this low achievement are the lack of variety in literacy activities, the lack of interaction between students and teachers, and the limited collection of reading books that are interesting and relevant to students' interests. To increase the effectiveness of literacy programs, it is necessary to carry out a variety of more interactive activities such as group discussions or presentations, the provision of more diverse reading sources, and increased teacher involvement as facilitators in accompanying the morning literacy process.

The implication of this study is that morning literacy habituation needs to be followed by additional strategic steps to improve students' reading comprehension skills effectively. The results of this study provide important information for schools and education policy makers to strengthen the implementation of the School Literacy Movement (GLS). The limitations in this study include the limited number of samples that only cover one class and the limited research time so that the results may not fully reflect the broader conditions. For this reason, the next research suggestion is to conduct further research with a wider and varied sample coverage, as well as explore more diverse and innovative literacy interventions to identify best practices in improving students' reading comprehension skills nationally.

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